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Farmers Attitudes towards Conservation of Olive Baboons in Kainji Lake National Park, Nigeria

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Abstract

For conservation efforts to be deemed successful, local perceptions and attitudes towards conservation have to be put into consideration. A weak tolerance for wildlife can jeopardize conservation efforts. Studies on attitudes and perception of communities around Protected areas help to comprehend and analyze their needs and aspirations. This study was therefore conducted to elicit information on farmers' attitudes towards conservation of olive baboons in Kainji Lake National Park (KLNP), Nigeria. Nine communities around KLNP were randomly selected and a structured questionnaire (n=117) was administered to farmers to elicit information on their socio economic characteristics and attitudes towards conservation of olive baboons in KLNP using a three-point Likert scale. A larger percentage (98.3%) of the farmers around KLNP were males. Most of them (37.6%) were between 41 and 50 years. There were more uneducated farmers (68.4%) and most of the respondents (86.3) practiced farming as a major source of income. Most of the farmers (59.8%) had a positive attitude towards the conservation of olive baboons in KLNP. The positive attitude was attributed to farmers' cultural beliefs about olive baboons, the absence of perceived threats to their lives and perceived economic benefits accruable from the establishment of the park within their communities. The Park management team should consolidate their efforts at improving the livelihood of farmers around the park and other support zone communities in order to sustain their cooperation and positive attitude towards the conservation of olive baboons in Kainji Lake National Park

Keywords: Attitude to conservation, Attitudinal statement, olive baboons, Kainji Lake National Park

INTRODUCTION

For conservation efforts to be deemed successful, local perceptions and attitudes towards conservation have to be put into consideration because a weak tolerance for wildlife and negative attitude towards Protected Areas can jeopardize conservation efforts. Attitude can be described as the predisposition to feel, think or act in a particular way with some degree of consistency. Conducting research on attitudes and perception of communities around Protected Areas helps to comprehend and analyze their needs and aspiration. Attitudinal studies facilitate the eliciting of nations and believe systems local communities have on conservation programmes (Badola *et al.*2012). Conservation attitudes could evolve from either individuals or communities' perceptions and experiences (Infield and Namara, 2001). This could alter their value and thoughts or even ultimately enhance their welfare (Badola *et al.*2012). Protected Areas are often cited in rural communities usually predominated by farmers. Two thirds of protected areas around the world are located in less developed countries with their borders coming so close to overlap with rural communities (Zimmerer, 2006; Ogra and

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Badola, 2008). In fact, some of these protected areas have enclaves within the National Park where the locals still reside, as it is the case in Gashaka Gumti National Park, Nigeria (Odebiyi and Alarape, 2018). Studies on the attitude of farmers help to predict what could be their response towards conservation policies (Fiallo and Jacobson, 1995). Losses suffered by farmers can make them antagonistic and intolerant towards wild animals, thereby developing a negative attitude towards conservation (Nyhus *et al.* 2000). Crop raiding by primates has been established to be capable of undermining farmers' tolerance towards conservation. Several primate species have been reported to raid farmers' crops. Olive baboon (*Papio anubis*), being an example of primates belonging to the family *cercopithecidae* is among the widely reported crop raiders around Protected Areas in Nigeria and Sub Sahara Africa, by extension. It is therefore essential to elicit farmers' attitudes towards conservation of olive baboons in Kainji Lake National park (KLNP). Information about communities' attitudes towards conservation is vital in designing conservation education and public enlightenment programmes. Reports about conservation attitudes are often cite specific because cultural and ecological factors vary across the globe (Sarker and Roskaft, 2010). The aforementioned therefore necessitates the need to conduct a study on the attitude of farmers towards conservation of olive baboons in KLNP. Successful conservation of natural resources is partly premised on the attitude and perception of local communities (Badola *et al.* 2012). In order to ensure peaceful coexistence and cordial relationship between local communities and protected area managers, it is paramount to have an understanding of the attitudes of local communities towards wildlife conservation. It was on this note that a study was conducted to elicit information on farmers' attitudes towards conservation of olive baboons in Kainji Lake National Park Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Kainji Lake National Park covers a total area of 5,340.82 km². The park lies approximately between latitudes 9°40'N and 10° 30' N and longitudes 3 ° 30' E and 5° 50' E (Aremu *et al.* 2000).

Nine communities out of twenty communities that share a border with the Kainji Lake National Park boundaries were selected through a random sampling technique. The selected communities were Tunga jagafe, Gada Oli, Butata, Daba Woko, Tunga taya, Lamba gudu, Daba gono dawa, Sarabe and Tunga Ibrahim. Purposive sampling technique was used to administer questionnaires to farmers in the selected communities. The study focused on farmers that had encountered olive baboons on their farms and that showed a good knowledge of olive baboons. A total of 117 farmers were sampled. The questionnaire was designed to elicit vital information such as demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents. The attitude of the farmers to the conservation of olive baboons in Kainji Lake National Park was measured on a 3 point likert scale of "agree", "disagree", and "undecided" based on six statements. The scales were rated as: Agree=3; Undecided=2; Disagree=1. The minimum expected score was 6 while the maximum expected score was 18. Interpreters assisted in collecting data from uneducated farmers.

Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were used to describe the socio demographic characteristics of the farmers.

RESULTS

A more significant percentage (98.3%) of farmers around KLNP were male while most of them (37.6%) were between the ages of 41 and 50 years old. Being a rural community, there were more uneducated farmers (68.4%). Most of the respondents (86.3%) practiced farming as a significant source of income. Table 1 shows the attitude statements of the farmers towards the conservation of olive baboons in KLNP. The mean score was 10.12. The summary of the attitudinal score, as presented in table 2 indicates that the majority (59.8%) of the respondents showed a favourable or positive attitude towards the conservation of olive baboons in KLNP.

It is remarkable to note that the majority of the farmers around KLNP had a positive attitude towards the conservation of olive baboons despite incidences of olive baboons raiding crops on their farmlands. Negative attitude towards the conservation of olive baboons was anticipated as reported in similar researches conducted in other protected areas. For instance crop damage by elephants (*Loxodonta africana*), hippopotamus

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(*Hippopotamus amphibius*) and bush pigs (*Potamochoerus porcus*) influenced the attitude of the local population to Maputo Elephant Reserve, Mozambique; whereby people with damage experiences were more negative (De Boer and Banquete, 1998). Kidegheso et al. (2006) tested and accepted the hypothesis that local communities that experience more losses from wildlife conservation are less likely to support protected areas.

However the finding of the positive attitude of farmers around KLNP towards the conservation of olive baboons notwithstanding the damage caused on their farmland is not an isolated case. Despite the destruction of farm produce by wild animals and other conservation induced costs, communities around Gashaka Gumti National Park, Taraba State held a positive view of conservation in the park (Odebiyi et al., 2015). In spite of records of human-wildlife conflict in mangrove forests in India, the local communities still exhibited a positive attitude towards the conservation of the forests (Badola et al., 2012). Seventy-four percent of local people sampled in the Annapurna Area in Nepal encountered wildlife depredation problems, yet an overwhelming majority showed favourable attitudes towards the conservation area (Mehta and Heinen, 2001). Apart from the mean score pooled from all the responses to the attitudinal statements which indicated that most of the respondents had a positive disposition towards conservation of olive baboons, the farmers' responses to some of the statements further showed that they were tolerant of olive baboons. Alarape et al. (2015) expressed the view that methods adopted by farmers to deter raiding animals reflect their level of tolerance towards the animal. When farmers around KLNP were asked to respond to the following statements; "the best way to deal with baboon on farmland is to kill them; baboons should be removed completely from the park; I support the use of poisons on my farm to prevent baboons from destroying crops planted; traps that injure or kill baboon should be used by farmers" a very impressive majority disagreed with those statements. This showed the tolerance of the farming communities towards the conservation of olive baboons. Our interaction with farmers gave an insight into explaining what accounted for their tolerance towards the crop-raiding baboons and their conservation.

The culture of the farmers explains why they were tolerant of the crop raiders. The study site comprises communities that are dominated by the Hausa tribe that forbids the consumption of monkeys. So even if they acted in retribution by killing the olive baboons, it would neither be suitable for consumption nor sale in contrast to other big games like the antelopes with no cultural restriction on their consumption. In other words, attitudes vary with location. Attitude towards wildlife is hardly the same across space because the contributory factors are spatially heterogeneous (Sitati et al., 2003; Naughton-Treves and Treves, 2005). Furthermore, the farmers in KLNP did not consider the raiding baboons as a threat to their lives (because no animal taking human lives is tolerated; Naughton-Treves and Treves, 2005), but only to their crops except in few cases where the baboons chased the farmers in the form of reprisal attacks.

The tolerance of the farmers could also be a function of the fear of being arrested and prosecuted. Olive baboons are protected by law and as such, the killing of such animals could attract the wrath of the law if caught. Some of the farmers said the reason why they would not consider shooting the animals when they sighted them on their farm was that, sometimes the rangers traced the sound of gunshots; which we equally experienced during our fieldwork.

We also found out that perceived economic benefits derived from the establishment and continued existence of the National Park made them have a favourable disposition toward the conservation of the wild animals in the park. They felt that the outright elimination of these raiding animals could amount to the economic benefits being severed. These economic benefits may not necessarily be directly accrueable to them and as such can be referred to as being direct or indirect benefits. Some of these benefits included employment opportunities for their relatives working in the National park, training on bee keeping and other income-generating opportunities, sensitization programmes, ecotourism related ventures, Shea butter processing machines, credit facilities, provision of social amenities such as portable water, rehabilitation of dilapidated classrooms etc. Other conservation-based non-governmental organizations like the Global Environment Facility (GEF) also collaborates with the park authority to execute community development projects and programmes. So even if they are not satisfied with the efforts of the management of National park in contributing to their livelihoods,

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they take solace in other indirect benefits that the establishment of the National park has brought to their communities at large.

Other authors lend their voice to the connection between local communities' positive attitude toward conservation and economic benefits derived from the protected areas. Despite human-wildlife conflicts in Nepal's Chitwan National Park, the local people associated income earned from tourist activities with having tigers in Chitwan and according to Carter *et al.* (2014), that likely explained in part why they expressed a more positive attitude towards tigers. The socio-economic conditions of local communities around the Bhitarkanika Conservation Area, India influenced their attitudes more than human wildlife conflict (Badola et al., 2012). Participation in training and benefits from tourism were among the significant predictors of local attitudes in the Annapurna Conservation Area (Mehta and Heinen, 2001). Odebiyi et al. (2015) attributed the positive attitude of the local communities around Gashaka Gumti National Park to the income they generated from tourists and employment opportunities with protected areas, among other factors. All these underscore the need for attitudinal studies as well as the determinants or predictors of attitudes. Studying attitudes will guide policymakers not only in formulating appropriate policies but policies that can be implemented for the conservation of wildlife because such studies help to identify and understand their needs and aspiration. Knowing what informs the attitude of local communities can be adopted in designing intervention programmes and mitigative measures where there are cases of human wildlife conflicts.

CONCLUSION

The majority of the farmers around Kainji Lake National Park had a positive attitude towards the conservation of olive baboons. Their positive attitude was evidenced in their response to the attitudinal statements. The positive attitude was attributed to farmers' cultural beliefs about olive baboons, absence of perceived threat to their lives and perceived economic benefits accruable from the establishment of the park within their communities. Kainji Lake National Park management team should consolidate their efforts at improving the livelihoods of farmers around the park and other support zone communities in order to sustain their cooperation and positive attitude towards the conservation of olive baboons in Kainji Lake National Park, Nigeria.

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LEGEND

Table 1: Attitudinal Statements of Farmers towards Conservation of Olive baboons in Kainji Lake National Park

Table 2: Summary of attitudinal scores of Farmers around Kainji Lake National Park

ABBREVIATIONS

GEF: Global Environment Facility

KLNP: Kainji Lake National Park

Table 1

STATEMENTS	A	U	D	X	Std
The best way to deal with baboons on farmland is to kill them	27 (23.1%)	12(10.3%)	78(66.6%)	1.56	0.84
Baboons should be removed completely from the park	40 (34.2%)	3(2.6%)	74(63.2%)	1.71	0.95
I support the use of poisons on my farm to prevent baboons from destroying crops	39 (33.3%)	3(2.6%)	75(64.1%)	1.69	0.94
Traps that injure or kill baboon should be used by farmers	42 (35.9%)	4(3.4%)	71(60.7%)	1.75	0.96
I do not believe in using scare crow to prevent baboons on my farm	33 (28.2%)	4(3.4%)	80(68.4%)	1.60	0.90
Baboons do not have any usefulness in the national park and the environment	45 (38.5%)	4(3.4%)	68(58.1%)	1.80	0.97

A=Agree, U=Undecided, D=Disagree, X= Mean, Std= Standard deviation

Mean: 10.12

Table 2

Attitude score	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Favourable 6-10	70	59.8
Unfavourable 11-18	47	40.2
Total	117	100.0